

HUMAN RESOURCES IN TOURISM AND HOSPITALITY**Mukhammadiyah Nodira**Lecturer at "Silk Road" international university
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Annotation: A human resource is a single person or employee within an organization and part of the overall personnel or workforce of that company. A human resource is one person within a company's overall workforce, with each person lending their skills and talents to the organization to help it succeed. Any person willing to trade their labor, knowledge, or time for compensation in an effort to improve the organization is a human resource. It doesn't matter if they're part-time, full-time, freelance, or contract employees.

Key words: Companies, Smart systems, Department, Management, interpersonal conflicts.

The goal of human resources is to use a company's people most effectively. Human resources might deal with issues such as:

- [Compensation](#) and benefits
- Recruiting and hiring employees
- Onboarding
- Performance management
- Training
- Organization development and culture

These areas each contribute to employee satisfaction and performance. By attending to these different concerns, human resources can ensure a high-functioning and effective workforce, which in turn helps the company reach its goals and objectives more efficiently.

The human resources department also ensures the company is adhering to labor regulations and works to keep the environment free from harassment and other impediments to a strong workforce.

Some people take issue with regarding employees as "resources." In their view, to consider workers as human resources commodifies them and reduces them to a figure on a balance sheet, or a means to an end. Instead, they promote renaming "human resources" to better encourage the full development of the human workforce.

Many of the functions of a human resource may in some cases be executed by non-human resources. In other words, robots or computers sometimes replace human employees, especially in hazardous conditions or for repetitive tasks. This is called automation, and it can greatly improve efficiency.

For example, you may often find robots on production lines, such as for cars. Automating certain parts of the production can increase production speed, but humans are still needed for some tasks, especially those that involve critical thinking.

Human resources functions may also be executed by specialized departments or staff. Instead of a general human resources manager, there may be a compensation and benefits manager, a training supervisor, or an employee recruitment specialist. Such specialization allows for greater efficiency and, often, improved profitability.

HR can help propel this transformation by facilitating positive change in these three key areas, as well as with nine imperatives that radiate out from them.

Organizations that can reallocate talent in step with their strategic plans are [more than twice as likely to outperform](#) their peers. To link talent to value, the best talent should be shifted into critical value-driving roles. That means moving away from a traditional approach, in which critical roles and talent are interchangeable and based on hierarchy.

Getting the best people into the most important roles requires a disciplined look at where the organization really creates value and [how top talent contributes](#). Consider Tesla's effort to create a culture of fast-moving innovation, or Apple's obsessive focus on user experience. These cultural priorities are at the core of these companies' value agendas. The roles needed to turn such priorities into value are often related to R&D and filled with talented, creative people.

To enable this shift, HR should manage talent rigorously by building an analytics capability to mine data to hire, develop, and retain the best employees. HR business partners, who articulate these staffing needs to the executive management team, should consider themselves internal service providers that ensure high returns on human-capital investments. For example, to engage business leaders in a regular review of talent, they can develop semiautomated data dashboards that track the most important metrics for critical roles.

Create the best employee experience possible

Companies know that a better employee experience means a better bottom line. Successful organizations work together with their people to create personalized, authentic, and motivating experiences that tap into purpose to strengthen individual, team, and company performance.

For instance, as a part of a multiyear agile transformation, a large European bank worked to establish an in-house agile academy led jointly by coaches and the HR function to drive capability building for the transformation.

To be successful, a transformation should touch every facet of an organization—people, process, strategy, structure, and technology. HR can help create an iterative approach by developing core elements of the people-management process, including new career paths for agile teams, revamped performance management, and capability building. It should lead by example as well, by [shifting to agile “flow to work” pools](#) in which individuals are staffed to prioritized tasks.

HR should be a strategic partner for the business in this regard, by ensuring that the right talent is in place to deliver on core company objectives. HR can also drive workforce planning by reviewing how disruptive trends affect employees, identifying future core capabilities, and assessing how supply and demand apply to future skills gaps.

Moving to a skills focus also requires innovative sourcing to meet specific work-activity needs (for example, the gig economy and automation), and changing which roles companies need to source with traditional full-time-equivalent positions and which can be done by temporary workers or contractors. In the survey with global executives, about 70 percent said that two years from now they expect to use more temporary workers and contractors than they did before the COVID-19 crisis.

Companies that [make decisions at the right organizational level](#) and that have fewer reporting layers are more likely to deliver consistently on quality, velocity, and performance outcomes and thus outperform their industry peers. The pandemic has trained the spotlight on the power of fast decision making, as many organizations have had to move dramatically more quickly than they had originally envisioned. For example, one retailer had a plan for curbside delivery that would take 18 months to roll out; once the COVID-19 crisis hit, the plan went operational in just two days.

HR can help with strong decision making by [empowering employees](#) to take risks in a culture that rewards them for doing so. McKinsey research revealed that employees who are empowered to make decisions and who

receive sufficient coaching from leaders were three times more likely to say that their companies' delegated decisions were both [high quality and speedy](#).

More specifically, HR can help deliver organizational excellence in the following four ways:

- First, HR should become a partner with senior and line managers in strategy execution, helping to move planning from the conference room to the marketplace.
- Second, it should become an expert in the way work is organized and executed, delivering administrative efficiency to ensure that costs are reduced while quality is maintained.
- Third, it should become a champion for employees, vigorously representing their concerns to senior management and at the same time working to increase employee contribution; that is, employees' commitment to the organization and their ability to deliver results.
- And finally, HR should become an agent of continuous transformation, shaping processes and a culture that together improve an organization's capacity for change.

Make no mistake: this new agenda for HR is a radical departure from the status quo. In most companies today, HR is sanctioned mainly to play policy police and regulatory watchdog. It handles the paperwork involved in hiring and firing, manages the bureaucratic aspects of benefits, and administers compensation decisions made by others. When it is more empowered by senior management, it might oversee recruiting, manage training and development programs, or design initiatives to increase workplace diversity. But the fact remains: the activities of HR appear to be—and often are—disconnected from the real work of the organization. The new agenda, however, would mean that every one of HR's activities would in some concrete way help the company better serve its customers or otherwise increase shareholder value.

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